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In vitro and in vivo evaluation of actively targetable solid lipid nanoparticles of paclitaxel and cisplatin for ovarian cancer

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Introduction: Cancer refers to one of the large number of diseases characterized by the development of abnormal cells that divide uncontrollably and have the ability to infiltrate and destroy normal body tissue. Ovarian Cancer is major problem for women. Nanoparticles offer an alternative delivery system for cancer therapy that have the potential to control the release rate of drug, improve the drug pharmacokinetics and biodistribution, and reduce drug toxicity. Due to their small size, nanoparticles with entrapped drugs may penetrate tumors due to the discontinuous and leaky nature of the microvasculature of tumors.

Material and Method: Therefore, in the present study we have developed Paclitaxel-loaded SLNs and Cisplatin-loaded SLNs by Microemulsion followed by probe sonication technique using Stearic acid as lipid and stabilized of Mixture of surfactants. In this study 3² Full Factorial design was employed for optimizing the concentration of lipid as Stearic acid and Surfactant (Soya lecithin) for the nanoparticles.

Result and Discussion: The SLNs of Paclitaxel and Cisplatin met all the requirements of a colloidal drug delivery system. They had particle size in nanosize; their size distribution was narrow and all the particles were in spherical shape. The SLNs of Paclitaxel and Cisplatin separately prepared for intravenous simultaneous delivery to obtain optimal therapeutic efficacy against ovarian cancer. Further, improvement of tissue distribution of Cisplatin & Paclitaxel with the help of Verapamil was attempted in the current work and impact of Verapamil, a P-gp modulator, on the availability of Paclitaxel & Cisplatin was checked.

Conclusion: The tissue distribution of Paclitaxel and Cisplatin was significantly increased by co-administration of Verapamil.

Keywords: Paclitaxel, Cisplatin, Solid Lipid Nanoparticles, Ovarian Cancer, Verapamil

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